

«WAR IS PEACE, FREEDOM IS SLAVERY,
IGNORANCE IS STRENGTH»

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Annotation: *The article deals with the problem of individual freedom, the relationship between the individual and the state. What attracts the reader in the artistic and journalistic prose of this author forbidden in totalitarian countries?*

First of all, the most acute problems of political and cultural life of the 40s of the XX century, which continue to be relevant today. As well as objectivity in assessing events and a bright author's personality, multiplied by true literary skill.

Keywords: *permutation of numbers, antipode, absurdity, doublethink, totalitarian power, individual*

«If you feel that it's worth staying human –
even if it doesn't give you anything - you still beat them!»

A novel that has been closely studied for more than 7 decades not only by literary critics, but also by politicians, sociologists, anthropologists and philosophers. "1984" - according to the versions of various publishers in the top of the best books of the ten-/century/ of all times and peoples, the leader of sales on Amazon, the best-selling book in Uzbekistan over the past decade (with sales only growing every year). And did you know that: in addition to the events in the USSR and Eastern Europe and his own story "Animal Farm", Zamyatin's dystopia "We" inspired the creation of Orwell's novel, from which many ideas, atmosphere, plot, main characters and symbolism were borrowed; initially, the novel had other versions of names - "The Last Man in Europe" and "The Living and the Dead"; according to legend, the name "1984" was chosen by the author by rearranging the last 2 digits of the year when the novel was created (1948); L. Trotsky and I. Stalin served as prototypes of the characters; the novel was banned in the USSR until 1988; this is the last work of the author, who died in poverty and loneliness a year after publication; the calendar year 1984 was declared the year of Orwell by UNESCO; 2 authors (Burgess and Gyorgy Dalosh) wrote their sequels of the novel, titled them the same - "1985" A classic dystopian novel, the complete antipode of Huxley's "Brave New World" with his absurdity-driven "consumer society", to which Orwell opposes the equally delusional "society of ideas". The plot is based on the political and social structure that developed on Earth by the end of the XX century, the clash of the individual and the state, based on hatred. After the Third World War in the

middle of the century, the world was divided into only 3 states - Oceania (territories of North and South America, Great Britain, South Africa, Australia and Oceania), Eurasia (USSR, Europe, Turkey) and East Asia (China, Mongolia, Korea, Japan, India). The world lives in poverty and ruin. All 3 countries have the same military potential and social structure, which is a hierarchy of the Upper strata of society (Internal Party), the Middle (members of the External Party) and the Lower ("proletariat", i.e. "proletariat"). The picture of the world, where totalitarian power is elevated to the absolute, is depicted in an unusually realistic way.

The place of action is Oceania, the First Military Air Zone (Great Britain), London and its environs. The inhabitants of the country are deprived of civil rights and individuality. In addition to the cult of Big Brother and unquestioning submission to the authorities, everyone is obliged to adhere to asexual views. Love is considered a thoughtcrime, sex is possible only for reproductive purposes. Every step of the party members is monitored by television screens that even read facial expressions and gestures. History is constantly being rewritten, the language is being "reformed" (simplified) into a new language. A meager stock of words and abbreviations is enough to express thoughts. A new ideology is taking root – doublethink. War is peace, freedom is slavery, ignorance is power. Power is not a means; it is an end. The main character is an unremarkable employee of the Ministry of Truth, 39-year-old Winston Smith, whose inner protest (thoughtcrime) begins with disappointment in the veracity of the Party and keeping a diary, and ends with a forbidden relationship with a woman, Julia, and an attempt to join an underground anti-government Brotherhood. But will a small person be able to resist a large system where the main task of the state is to destroy the Individual?! The people are constantly instilled with hatred of enemies and love for their ubiquitous leader - the Elder Brother. All information about the past is corrected to the advantage of the government, and the poor financial situation of people and the stratification of society is carefully covered with the veil of socialism. Winston Smith is the only normal person who distinguishes truth from lies, trying to fight against the almighty party. . The party needs a man, an unconscious man, not a man. The structure of the country in the book is really frightening: will the party rule forever?

The atmosphere of fear and hopelessness is realistic. The colors are condensed to 2 main colors - gray and red. The color of this book is gray, mercilessly gray: skin, sky, food, floor, walls, mind, life itself. Additional piquancy is given by the general decline, hard work, exploitation, chronic diseases and ailments.

Despite the simplicity of the language, the phantasmagoric nature of the plot is complemented by metaphor, oxymorons, symbolism and grotesque. Many call Orwell a prophet, although some critics still insist that this is not a dystopia at all, but a satire on modern society or a novel-a warning that the author did not set out to allegorically depict the modern model of the state or write an anti-Stalinist pamphlet, or that this is a

novel about love in general. In any case, this is a novel about the relationship between the Individual and the System, the Citizen and the State.

On the pages of this book, you can understand the psychology of both the top and the bottom; the work of the propaganda machine - today we say one thing, and tomorrow we categorically say another, pretending that yesterday did not exist.

It seems that each reader will have their own conclusions, while ours (as after Zamyatin's "We") conclude that the main thing is to always and under any circumstances remain human.

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